

Bayesian Cure Rate Model: Exploring Laplacian-P-Splines and Metropolis-Langevin-within-GIBBS Sampling Approaches

Vijai B¹, Jayashree PR², Ponnuraja C³

ABSTRACT

Introduction: In the context of survival analysis, the mixture cure model provides a powerful framework for analyzing time-to-event data where a subset of the population may never experience the event of interest. This model assumes that the study population is composed of two latent subgroups: cured individuals, who will never encounter the event regardless of the follow-up duration, and susceptible individuals, who remain at risk and may eventually experience the event. Traditional survival models like Cox's proportional hazards model are not designed to handle such data, thereby necessitating models that can estimate not only time-to-event but also the probability of cure. **Aim & Objective:** This paper aims to develop and evaluate a sampling-free, computationally efficient Bayesian inference approach for the mixture cure model by utilizing penalized B-splines and Laplace approximations. The objective is to achieve rapid and accurate posterior inference for both incidence and latency components of the model, without relying on computationally intensive Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling. **Methodology:** We propose a novel approach called the Laplacian P-splines for Mixed Cure (LPSMC) model, which integrates Laplace approximations with P-spline-based hazard modeling. This method allows smooth estimation of survival curves and cure probabilities with credible intervals, while significantly reducing computation time. To benchmark the proposed approach, a fully stochastic algorithm, Metropolis-Langevin-within-Gibbs (MLWG) sampling, is implemented as a comparison baseline. Simulation studies are conducted using two sample sizes (200 and 300), each evaluated under two MCMC chain lengths (5000 and 7000), allowing for a thorough investigation of accuracy, uncertainty quantification, and convergence behavior across scenarios. **Results:** The simulation results demonstrate that the LPSMC method consistently provides accurate estimates of regression coefficients, cure fractions, and survival curves, with reduced bias, empirical standard error (ESE), and root mean square error (RMSE) as the sample size increases. Additionally, credible intervals obtained through Laplace approximations show coverage probabilities close to nominal levels. Compared to the MLWG sampler, the LPSMC approach achieves comparable statistical performance with a substantial gain in computational efficiency, making it a practical alternative for routine Bayesian inference in mixed cure models. **Conclusion:** The proposed LPSMC method effectively leverages the flexibility of penalized splines and the efficiency of Laplace's method to provide a robust, scalable alternative to MCMC for posterior inference in cure models. This framework offers a valuable tool for survival analysis in settings where a cured proportion is present, especially in clinical research where both model interpretability and computational speed are essential.

Keywords: Approximate Bayesian inference, Metropolis-Langevin-within-Gibbs, Laplacian-P-splines mixture cure rate, Survival analysis

Author(s) Details:

1. Research Scholar, Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Dharmamurthi Rao Bahadur Calavala Cunnan Chetty's Hindu College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, **Email:** vijai.stats@gmail.com
2. Associate Professor, Department of Statistics, Presidency College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India; **Email:** vprjaya@gmail.com
3. Scientist – 'F', Head and Department of Statistics, ICMR – National Institute for Research in Tuberculosis, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India; **Email:** cponnuraja@gmail.com

Corresponding Address: Vijai B, Research Scholar, Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics, Dharmamurthi Rao Bahadur Calavala Cunnan Chetty's Hindu College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, **Email:** vijai.stats@gmail.com

Citation: Vijai B, Jayashree PR, Ponnuraja C. Bayesian cure rate model: Exploring Laplacian-P-Splines and Metropolis-Langevin-within-GIBBS Sampling Approaches. *Indian J Prev Soc Med*, 2025; 56 (3): 321-328. DOI <https://doi.org/>

Sequence of Article:

Submission: 10.06.2025 | Revision: 25.06.2025 | Accepted: 13.08.2025 | Published: 30.00.2025

Prior Publication: Nil; **Source of Funding:** Nil; **Conflicts of Interest:** None, **Article # 800/1176**

Introduction

In survival analysis, it is common to observe that some individuals do not experience the event of interest during the study period. These individuals are considered *cured*, meaning they are no longer at risk of the event. This leads to the population being classified into two subgroups: *susceptible* and *non-susceptible (cured)* individuals¹. Numerous fields of research use survival analysis, such as biology, public health, medicine, and epidemiology. The survival data is used to demonstrate time-to-event data modeling, which may be applied to either the time till death or to being alive, depending on the situation. The time until an occurrence of interest is referred to as the survival or failure time².

Survival analysis is widely applied in fields such as biology, public health, medicine, and epidemiology. It models *time-to-event* data, which can refer to the time until death, disease occurrence, relapse, or other key outcomes. The interval until an event is commonly referred to as the *survival time* or *failure time*^{3,4,5}. We are more interested in increasing the cure rate for the majority of illnesses than in extending the period until the event of interest. Traditional approaches like Cox's PH or the AFT model cannot be used to estimate the cured rate for such time-to-event data. Such data may be analysed using the cure model introduced by Boag (1949) and Berkson (1952)^{6,7}.

As medical advances improve long-term outcomes, interest has shifted from merely delaying the event to estimating the proportion of cured individuals. However, traditional survival models like Cox's PH or AFT models assume that all individuals are susceptible and do not allow for a cured fraction. To address this, cure models, introduced by Boag (1949) and Berkson & Gage (1952), were developed. The mixed cure model assumes a latent structure in which the population is composed of two types of individuals: *susceptible patients* who may eventually experience the event, and *non-susceptible (cured)* individuals who will not^{8,9}. Balogun and Jolayemi used this cure rate model to estimate the cure rate by modeling an infectious illness with co-infection data and estimating the cure rate using the exponential distribution¹⁰. The cure rate model is practical and helpful in a variety of fields, such as medical care, reliability, and finance^{10,11}. Barriga et al.¹², Oliveira, and Louzada^{13,14} state that the cure rate model was previously used to estimate loan recovery and to determine loan performance.

Recently, Bayesian approaches have been increasingly adopted for cure models due to their flexibility and capacity for incorporating prior information. Posterior inference is typically performed using Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods. However, despite their accuracy, MCMC methods are computationally intensive, often requiring long run times and suffering from convergence issues in complex models. To address this, researchers such as Gressani and colleagues have explored the use of Laplacian-P-splines and Laplace approximations for faster and more scalable Bayesian inference in survival models. These techniques have shown promise in efficiently estimating survival functions and time-varying parameters in both medical and epidemic contexts.

By applying the spline specification, smooth estimates of survival curves and functions of latent variables, along with the associated credible interval, can be obtained in seconds¹⁵. MCMC techniques are frequently used to sample from posterior distributions when the Bayesian paradigm is used to inference in survival models with a cure fraction. Despite being computationally practical, MCMC's repetitive nature sometimes requires lengthy sampling durations in order to explore the target space using chains that could have insufficient mixing and weak convergence. To assess the ability of the produced posterior samples. According to Gressani and Lambert¹⁶ and also Gressani, Faes, and Hens¹⁵, Laplacian-P-splines have previously shown potential in survival models also in epidemic models for estimating the time-varying reproduction number Gressani et al¹⁷; Gressani, Faes, and Hens¹⁸; Sumalinab¹⁹.

In this study, we introduce a Bayesian inference method for mixed cure models, LPSMC (Laplacian P-splines for Mixed Cure models), that leverages penalized B-splines and Laplace approximations for efficient estimation of survival curves and cure fractions. This method offers a faster, sampling-free alternative to MCMC, while maintaining accuracy in posterior approximation. We also evaluate a fully stochastic approach, the Metropolis-Langevin-within-Gibbs (MLWG) sampler, which integrates Langevin dynamics with Gibbs sampling for improved posterior exploration. Through extensive simulation studies, we compare these two approaches across varying sample sizes, cure rates, and censoring levels.

Our findings demonstrate that LPSMC offers strong performance in terms of estimation accuracy and credible interval coverage, while significantly reducing computational cost, highlighting its potential for practical applications in complex survival analysis scenarios.

Materials and Methods

To distinguish individuals who have been cured and those who are at risk of suffering the event of interest in the future, the methodology used in this work involves developing a Bayesian inference strategy for the mixed cure survival models, which is a useful expansion of traditional time-to-event models. Bayesian modelling is essential to survival analysis because it provides flexibility in managing complicated data structures and permits the incorporation of prior knowledge. To create a sampling-free method in this study uses two cutting-edge methods, Metropolis-Langevin-within-Gibbs (MLWG) sampling and Laplacian P-splines (LPS) to examine the accuracy and efficacy of Bayesian survival models. These approaches enhance traditional time-to-event models by accommodating the presence of cured individuals and by enabling flexible hazard function estimation through penalized B-splines. Bayesian modelling is advantageous in survival analysis as it allows for the incorporation of prior knowledge and facilitates inference under complex data structures. The MLWG sampler integrates Metropolis-Hastings and Langevin dynamics within a Gibbs sampling framework, offering a stochastic inference mechanism. In contrast, the LPSMC method employs Laplace approximations to avoid intensive sampling, which significantly reduces computational burden while maintaining inference accuracy.

A numerical simulation study was conducted to assess the performance of the LPSMC approach. Survival data were synthetically generated to reflect realistic conditions, including varying cure rates and right-censoring. The incidence component was modelled using a logistic regression function, defined as $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{X}_i) = \mathbf{1} / [1 + \exp(-\beta_0 - \beta_1 X_{i1} - \beta_2 X_{i2})]$, models the incidence component. Here, we may add a combination of continuous and binary variables since X_{i1} is a standard normal variate ($X_{i1} \sim N(0, 1)$) and $X_{i2} \sim \text{Bern}(0.5)$ is a Bernoulli random variable. The cure status B_i was generated as a Bernoulli variable with success probability $p(X_i)$, i.e., in Bi-Bern ($p(X_i)$), indicating whether the individual belongs to the cured group.

For uncured individuals, survival times T_i were simulated from a Weibull distribution under the Cox proportional hazards model framework. The model used a scale parameter ($\nu = 0.25$) and shape parameter ($k = 1.45$). Additional covariates Z_i were introduced in the latency component, where $Z_{i1} \sim N(0, 1)$ and $Z_{i2} \sim \text{Bern}(0.5)$, independent of X_i . Right-censoring times C_i were independently sampled from an exponential distribution with mean $1/\mu_c$, ensuring realistic censoring in the study. Survival times were truncated at $T_i = 8$ for cured individuals ($B_i = 1$), reflecting the absence of event occurrence within the observation period.

Estimation Procedure and Performance Metrics

We conducted simulation studies for two sample sizes: $n = 200$ and $n = 300$. For each scenario, 500 Monte Carlo replications were performed. Parameter estimation was carried out using the 'mixcurepls' package in R (version 4.3.2). The performance of the LPSMC model was evaluated using the following criteria:

- **Bias:** the mean difference between estimated and true parameter values.
- **Empirical Standard Error (ESE):** the standard deviation of estimates across replications.
- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):** a combined measure of bias and variance.
- **Coverage Probability:** the proportion of times the true parameter lies within the 90% and 95% credible intervals.

To benchmark against stochastic sampling, we also applied the MLWG sampler with two different MCMC chain lengths (5000 and 7000), each with a burn-in of 3000 iterations. This enabled us to compare convergence, estimation accuracy, and computational stability between LPSMC and MLWG under identical data scenarios.

Graphical Evaluation:

Survival function estimation accuracy was visually assessed using simulated survival curves. For each setting, the true survival function was compared with the point wise median from 500 simulated curves, and 95% credible intervals were plotted to assess uncertainty. Additional visualization tools included:

- **Box plots** of Average Squared Error (ASE) for model parameters, illustrating variability and inter-quartile range.
- **Density plots** of ASE to highlight the frequency distribution and concentration of low-error estimates.

Results

The simulation study assessed the statistical performance of the LPSMC technique under various sample sizes and data conditions. **Table-1** summarizes the regression coefficient estimates obtained using the LPSMC approach for sample sizes of $n = 200$ and $n = 300$, across 500 replications. The performance metrics evaluated include bias, empirical standard error (ESE), root mean square error (RMSE), and coverage probabilities for the 90% and 95% credible intervals. The results demonstrate a clear improvement in estimation accuracy with increasing sample size. Specifically, bias, ESE, and RMSE values consistently decreased as the sample size increased from 200 to 300. This pattern reflects enhanced model stability and precision with more information. Additionally, coverage probabilities closely matched the nominal levels, indicating that the credible intervals were well-calibrated and effective in capturing true parameter uncertainty.

Table-1: Simulation results for the regression coefficients with LPS

Scenario	Parameters	Mean	Bias	ESE	RMSE	CP _{90%}	CP _{95%}
Scenario 1 (n = 200)	$\beta_1=0.7$	0.68	-0.02	0.323	0.323	88.4	95.8
	$\beta_1=-1.15$	-1.194	-0.044	0.318	0.321	90.4	94.2
	$\beta_2=0.95$	1.004	0.054	0.483	0.486	91.2	96.4
	$\gamma_1=0.1$	-0.097	0.003	0.111	0.111	90.4	94.6
	$\gamma_1=0.25$	0.223	-0.027	0.232	0.234	87.6	95.0
Scenario 1 (n = 300)	$\beta_0=0.7$	0.72	0.02	0.249	0.249	91	96.6
	$\beta_1=-1.15$	-1.181	-0.031	0.24	0.242	91.6	94.8
	$\beta_2=0.95$	0.953	0.003	0.39	0.39	90.6	94.2
	$\gamma_1=-0.1$	-0.101	-0.001	0.092	0.092	89.6	94.4
	$\gamma_2=0.25$	0.243	-0.007	0.184	0.184	89	96.4
Scenario 2 (n = 200)	$\beta_0=1.25$	1.269	0.019	0.294	0.294	89.8	94.0
	$\beta_1=-0.75$	-0.762	-0.012	0.221	0.221	91.8	95.0
	$\beta_2=0.45$	0.499	0.049	0.414	0.416	90.6	95.0
	$\gamma_1=-0.1$	-0.096	0.004	0.092	0.092	87.6	94.0
	$\gamma_2=0.25$	0.209	0.009	0.178	0.178	90.4	95.4
Scenario 2 (n = 300)	$\beta_0=1.25$	1.28	0.03	0.228	0.23	91.4	95.6
	$\beta_1=-0.75$	-0.765	-0.015	0.182	0.183	91.0	95.6
	$\beta_2=0.45$	0.43	-0.02	0.33	0.33	89.0	94.8
	$\gamma_1=-0.1$	-0.103	-0.003	0.074	0.074	88.8	94.4
	$\gamma_2=0.2$	0.194	-0.006	0.15	0.15	87.2	94.8

The performance of the Metropolis-Langevin-within-Gibbs (MLWG) sampler was also evaluated with two chain lengths (5000 and 7000), and results are presented in **Tables- 2 and 3**. Both configurations produced similar outcomes, demonstrating stable convergence and reliable estimates across different sample sizes. These findings affirm the robustness of the MLWG sampler and serve as a comparative baseline for evaluating the LPSMC method. The low bias, decreasing ESE and RMSE with larger samples, and accurate coverage probabilities across scenarios demonstrate the robustness of our model and methodology under conditions reflective of practical survival analysis situations with a high rate of cured cases.

Table-2: Simulation results for the regression coefficients with MLWG of chain length 5000

Scenario	Parameters	Mean	Bias	ESE	RMSE	CP _{90%}	CP _{95%}
Scenario 1 (n = 200)	$\beta_1=0.7$	0.819	0.119	0.37	0.392	88.2	93.2
	$\beta_1=-1.15$	-1.28	-0.13	0.39	0.411	86.4	91.8
	$\beta_2=0.95$	1.096	0.146	1.45	1.455	89.2	93.8
	$\gamma_1=0.1$	-0.11	-0.01	0.11	0.112	89.8	95.0
	$\gamma_1=0.25$	0.218	-0.03	0.22	0.223	90	95.6
Scenario 1 (n = 300)	$\beta_0=0.7$	0.778	0.078	0.32	0.326	88.6	93.8
	$\beta_1=-1.15$	-1.25	-0.1	0.28	0.298	88.6	96.0
	$\beta_2=0.95$	1.068	0.118	0.47	0.483	87	93.0
	$\gamma_1=-01$	-0.1	-0	0.09	0.089	89.2	94.4
	$\gamma_2=-0.25$	0.225	-0.03	0.18	0.185	90.6	93.6
Scenario 2 (n = 200)	$\beta_0=1.25$	1.336	0.086	0.32	0.33	86.4	92.8
	$\beta_1=-0.75$	-0.79	-0.04	0.27	0.27	84.4	89.4
	$\beta_2=0.45$	0.483	0.033	0.46	0.463	87	92.8
	$\gamma_1=-01$	-0.11	-0.01	0.1	0.098	86	92.6
	$\gamma_2=-0.25$	0.193	-0.01	0.2	0.199	86.4	92.2
Scenario 2 (n = 300)	$\beta_0=1.25$	1.316	0.066	0.24	0.249	89.4	94.0
	$\beta_1=-0.75$	-0.8	-0.05	0.2	0.205	85.2	92.6
	$\beta_2=0.45$	0.469	0.019	0.35	0.347	88.2	94.6
	$\gamma_1=-01$	-0.1	0.004	0.08	0.075	90	93.4
	$\gamma_2=-0.2$	0.177	-0.02	0.15	0.156	86	92.8

Table-3: Simulation results for the regression coefficients with MLWG of chain length 7000

Scenario	Parameters	Mean	Bias	ESE	RMSE	CP _{90%}	CP _{95%}
Scenario 1 (n = 200)	$\beta_1=0.7$	0.8	0.1	0.573	0.581	89.0	94.4
	$\beta_1=-1.15$	-1.33	-0.18	0.636	0.66	85.4	92.2
	$\beta_2=0.95$	1.147	0.197	1.437	1.449	85.4	92.6
	$\gamma_1=0.1$	-0.101	-0.001	0.114	0.114	89.2	94.4
	$\gamma_1=0.25$	0.206	-0.044	0.221	0.225	90.0	95.6
Scenario 1 (n = 300)	$\beta_0=0.7$	0.805	0.105	0.339	0.355	88.4	94.0
	$\beta_1=-1.15$	-1.274	-0.124	0.301	0.325	87.4	94.4
	$\beta_2=0.95$	1.014	0.064	0.659	0.661	86.6	91.0
	$\gamma_1=-01$	-0.103	-0.003	0.091	0.091	90.6	94.6
	$\gamma_2=-0.25$	0.213	-0.037	0.183	0.186	88.2	93.8
Scenario 2 (n = 200)	$\beta_0=1.25$	1.32	0.07	0.29	0.298	88.8	95.2
	$\beta_1=-0.75$	-0.819	-0.069	0.243	0.252	88.8	93.6
	$\beta_2=0.45$	0.467	0.017	0.438	0.438	88.0	95.2
	$\gamma_1=-01$	-0.099	0.001	0.094	0.094	88.6	92.8
	$\gamma_2=-0.25$	0.195	-0.005	0.196	0.196	87.8	93.0
Scenario 2 (n = 300)	$\beta_0=1.25$	1.307	0.057	0.238	0.244	86.8	94.8
	$\beta_1=-0.75$	-0.788	-0.038	0.184	0.188	89.6	94.4
	$\beta_2=0.45$	0.465	0.015	0.341	0.341	89	95.0
	$\gamma_1=-01$	-0.1	0	0.074	0.074	90.6	95.6
	$\gamma_2=-0.2$	0.182	-0.018	0.151	0.152	88.8	94.2

Using the LPSMC approach, the survival curves for two simulation scenarios and two different sample sizes are computed and displayed in Figures 1a, 1b, 1c, and 1d. The aim of the survival function (solid black line) is compared to the point wise median of 500 simulated survival curves (dashed red line) to illustrate the degree of uncertainty in the survival estimations. Around the (black line), the shaded (gray) area represents the confidence intervals. A good concordance between estimated and actual survival functions is shown by the black and red lines' close alignment across time, demonstrating the model's ability to accurately represent underlying survival patterns. Visualizations such as box plots and density plots help with data understanding by providing simple insights into error distribution among samples. The box plot in the middle shows the distribution of the Average Squared Error (ASE) for parameter α across simulations. The line within the box represents the median ASE, while the box borders indicate the interquartile range (IQR). The concentration of most ASE values inside a small IQR implies consistently low estimating errors, which is consistent with findings from previous methodological studies.

Figure : 1a

Figure : 1b

Figure : 1c

Figure : 1d

Figure 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d: Survival Curves, Average Squared Error and density plots for two simulation scenarios using the LPS Markov Chain Approach with two different sample sizes

The density plot on the right provides a frequency-based perspective on ASE values, with a peak at lower ASE levels indicating that most estimates have minimal error, and a lighter right-hand tail illustrating a tiny fraction of higher ASE values. This density distribution is consistent with the reported resilience in parameter estimation across samples, as demonstrated by Monte Carlo simulation experiments in which low ASE concentrations suggest high estimator precision. Together, these visualization tools improve our comprehension of the simulated data's fit and provide a valuable tool for assessing model correctness across different sample situations.

The LPSMC model demonstrates strong performance in estimating regression coefficients and survival functions under various simulation conditions. The results indicate low bias, narrow error distributions, well-calibrated uncertainty estimates, and robust behavior across different sample sizes, validating the effectiveness of this approach for mixed-cure survival data analysis.

Conclusion

Especially for models with complicated likelihoods, where the traditional MCMC algorithms need long calculation times, approximate Bayesian inference techniques provide a novel solution. By allowing for the existence of a cure fraction, the mixed cure model is an interesting model class in survival analysis that goes beyond conventional proportional hazards models, which do not have an attribute of long-term survivors. In this work, we present a novel approach to fast Bayesian inference in the traditional mixed cure model, which combines P-splines for flexible modelling of baseline smooth quantities with the strength of Laplace approximations to (conditional) posterior distributions of latent variables.

With an analytically accessible gradient and log-likelihood curvature matrix, the LPSMC technique stands out for its ability to decrease computing performance and provide a framework that is entirely sampling-free as well as increase convergence, making it ideal for complicated survival models with big datasets. This computing advantage, along with the relatively easy way to find (approximate) credible intervals for functions of latent variables, has allowed for quick evaluation of survival data with a cure fraction. Furthermore, by providing a completely MCMC-based technique for inference in the mixed cure model, the MLWG selector improves the effectiveness of the sampling-free LPSMC approach. The numerical simulations performed for this study indicate that our suggested model predicts survival and cure rates with little bias. We intend to test this approach with actual data in further research and investigate alternative parametric models to observe their performance in real-world scenarios. The proposed methods have potential applications in a wide range of fields where accurate survival estimates are essential, such as healthcare, finance, and reliability engineering as a powerful tool for Bayesian survival analysis.

References

1. Patilea V, Van Keilegom I. A general approach for cure models in survival analysis. *The Annals of Statistics*. 2020 Aug 1; 48(4) : 2323-46.
2. Zhao G. Nonparametric and parametric survival analysis of censored data with possible violation of method assumptions. The University of North Carolina at Greensboro; 2008.
3. Peng Y, Zhang J. Estimation method of the semi-parametric mixture cure gamma frailty model. *Statistics in medicine*. 2008 Nov 10;27(25):5177-94.
4. Zhang J, Peng Y. A new estimation method for the semi-parametric accelerated failure time mixture cure model. *Statistics in medicine*. 2007 Jul 20;-26-(16):3157-71.
5. Corbiere F, Commenges D, Taylor JM, Joly P. A penalized likelihood approach for mixture cure models. *Statistics in medicine*. 2009 Feb 10; 28 (3):510-24.
6. Boag JW. Maximum likelihood estimates of the proportion of patients cured by cancer therapy. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*. 1949 Jan 1; 11(1):15-53.
7. Berkson J, Gage RP. Survival curve for cancer patients following treatment. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. 1952 Sep 1;47(259):501-15.
8. Corbiere F, Joly P. A SAS macro for parametric and semiparametric mixture cure models. *Computer methods and programs in biomedicine*. 2007 Feb 1;85(2):173-80.
9. Farewell VT. The use of mixture models for the analysis of survival data with long-term survivors. *Biometrics*. 1982 Dec 1:1041-6.
10. Balogun, O.S., Jolayemi, E.T.: Modelling of a cure rate model for TB with HIV co-infection. *Pac. J. Sci. Technol.* 18(1), 288–299 (2017).
11. Nelson WB. *Applied life data analysis*. John Wiley & Sons; 2005 Feb 25.

12. Barriga GD, Cancho VG, Louzada F. A non-default rate regression model for credit scoring. *Applied Stochastic Models in Business and Industry*. 2015 Nov; 31(6):846-61.
13. Oliveira MR, Louzada F. An evidence of link between default and loss of bank loans from the modelling of competing risks. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics and Management Studies*. 2014 Aug 19;3(1):30-7.
14. Oliveira MR, Louzada F. Recovery risk: Application of the latent competing risks model to non performing loans. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1408.4380*. 2014 Aug 19.
15. Gressani O, Faes C, Hens N. Laplacian-P-splines for Bayesian inference in the mixture cure model. *Statistics in Medicine*. 2022 Jun 30;41(14):2602-26.
16. Gressani O, Lambert P. Fast Bayesian inference using Laplace approximations in a flexible promotion time cure model based on P-splines. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*. 2018 Aug 1;124:151-67.
17. Gressani O, Wallinga J, Althaus CL, Hens N, Faes C. EpiLPS: A fast and flexible Bayesian tool for estimation of the time-varying reproduction number. *PLoS computational biology*. 2022 Oct 10; 18 (10):e1010618.
18. Gressani O, Faes C, Hens N. An approximate Bayesian approach for estimation of the instantaneous reproduction number under misreported epidemic data. *Biometrical Journal*. 2023 Aug; 65(6):2200024.
19. Sumalinab B, Gressani O, Hens N, Faes C. An efficient approach to nowcasting the time-varying reproduction number. *Epidemiology*. 2024 Jul 1; 35 (4):512-6.
20. Rue H., Martino S., Chopin N. Approximate Bayesian inference for latent Gaussian models by using Integrated Nested Laplace Approximations. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series B (Methodological)* 2009, 71, 319–392, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9868.2008.00700.x>.